

Special Issue Call for Papers

Journal of Law, Society, and Authority (JLSA)

Special Issue – December 2026 (English Edition)

The *Journal of Law, Society, and Authority (JLSA)* invites submissions for a peer-reviewed special issue dedicated to contemporary debates in international law, international relations, and security studies.

Special Issue Theme

International Order and the Question of the Use of Force Involving Iran: Geopolitical and Legal Dimensions

This special issue explores the legal, geopolitical, and strategic implications of contemporary developments involving Iran and their impact on international order, regional security, and the interpretation of norms governing the use of force within the framework of international law.

The issue welcomes analytically rigorous and interdisciplinary contributions adopting legal, political, strategic, or critical approaches.

Editorial Coordination

Guest Editors:

- **Prof. BELHOUL Nacim** - University of Blida 2 – Lounici Ali, Algeria
- **Dr. WANG Guangda** - China-Arab Research Center on Reform and Development, China
- **Prof. Hassan Abdullah Al-Da'jah** - Al-Hussein Bin Talal University, Jordan / Advisor to the Belt and Road Institute at Beijing University / Member of the International Council for Chinese Studies Scholars

Editor-In-Chief:

- **Prof. BOUSMAHA Nasreddine** - University of Oran 2 – Mohamed Ben Ahmed, Algeria

Scope and Indicative Themes

Contributions may address topics including, but are not limited to:

- International law and the regulation of the use of force.
- Interpretation of the UN Charter and collective security mechanisms.
- Regional security dynamics involving Iran and the Middle East.
- Maritime security and strategic trade routes.
- Energy security and geoeconomic transformations.
- Sanctions, power transitions, and emerging multipolarity.
- Non-state actors and asymmetric conflicts.
- Media, strategic communication, and information warfare.

Submission Guidelines

- **Language:** English only
- **Submission deadline:** 15 September 2026
- **Submission Email:** nassaiki@yahoo.fr

Author Guidelines

- **Official Manuscript Template (English Version):**
[Download the Official Manuscript Template-English version](#)
- **Author Guidelines:**
<https://revue.univ-oran2.dz/Revue/DSP/index.php/DSP/Author-guidelines>

Journal Indexing and Publication Framework

The *Journal of Law, Society, and Authority (JLSA)* is a peer-reviewed, open-access academic journal:

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